

MEANING OF MOTOR SKILLS IN THE FORMATION OF MOTOR SKILLS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Аннотация. В статье раскрывается исследование двигательной активности детей дошкольного возраста с помощью подвижных игр. Разработана программа с предложенной динамикой освоения двигательных умений и навыков у детей дошкольного возраста в процессе занятий по физическому воспитанию. В работе выявлена повышение значения разработанной методики по формированию двигательной активности детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: дошкольники, двигательная активность детей, подвижные игры, программа, формирование, методика.

Annotation. The article reveals a study of the motor activity of preschool children with the help of outdoor games. A program has been developed with the proposed dynamics of the development of motor skills in preschool children in the process of physical education classes. The work reveals an increase in the value of the developed methodology for the formation of motor activity of preschool children.

Key words: preschoolers, motor activity of children, outdoor games, program, formation, methodology.

Relevance. Preschool education is considered the primary and most important link in the education system. The upbringing of a healthy gene pool, full-fledged personnel, first of all, begins with this system. However, until now, this system has lagged behind in development. Over the past 20 years, the number of public preschool educational institutions has decreased by 45 percent. As a result, only 33 percent of preschool children are enrolled in preschool education institutions. (This figure is 99 percent in Denmark, 97 percent in Japan, and 95 percent in South Korea). Educational programs on the social, personal, emotional, speech, mathematical, physio-psychological, physical and creative development of children have not been introduced in preschool education institutions.

To date, the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted more than 30 regulatory documents, including "State requirements for the development of children of early and preschool age", the "First Step" curriculum and thematic planning developed in accordance with it in the context of age groups of children, theoretical and a practical complex of physical education, a working journal for instructors in physical education of preschool educational institutions.

This scientific work to a certain extent serves to fulfill the tasks outlined in the Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PP-2707 dated December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education for 2017-2021" and No. PP-3261 dated September 9, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of preschool education ", Decree No. UP-5198 dated September 30, 2017 "On measures to

radically improve the management of the preschool education system", as well as in the legal documents in this area.

The aim of the study is to develop a methodology for outdoor games used to form motor skills in preschool children. skills and abilities.

Research objectives:

scientific and practical substantiation of indicators of normative movements and analysis of daily active movements, as well as the level of physical development of preschool children in terms of age;

development of a program to improve the skills and abilities of preschool children in the process of physical education;

optimization of normative documents and activities of physical education instructors of preschool educational institutions;

Research methods. And analysis of literature, pedagogical observation, questioning, anthropometry, pulsometry, pedagogical experiment, mathematical and statistical methods.

In institutions of preschool education, the daily routine is organized through clearly defined activities in the following age groups: younger (3-4 years); middle (4-5 years); senior (5-6 years), preparatory (6-7 years). In an educational institution, educational work is carried out in 5 areas, the initial link is the organization of physical education and a healthy lifestyle.

With the regular organization of physical education classes, children develop motor skills and improve their skills. During some classes, the focus is on teaching children new physical exercises along with previously learned ones; during other classes, attention is paid to the degree of development of motor material by children. The implementation of the goals and objectives set before the physical education lesson, as well as the results achieved, are associated with the ability to correctly distribute classes into parts and activities in them (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Distribution into parts of the lesson, giving new knowledge and consolidating it according to the results

In the course of the study, on the basis of a physical education program, we gave a characteristic of the development of motor skills and skills of large, sensory and fine motor skills of preschoolers when performing movements. Appropriate outdoor games are chosen in order to consolidate the child's motor skills in performing basic motor exercises, such as walking, running, jumping, rolling, throwing, grabbing (receiving the ball), crawling, climbing, maintaining balance, as well as jumping from different heights, rolling balls to each other, developing a throw with two hands from below, from the chest, over the head (table 1).

Table 1

Recommended outdoor games for the development of motor skills and abilities of children from 5 to 7 years old

No.	Gross motor skills	Names of games that form motor skills and abilities	Fine motor skills	Names of games that form motor skills and abilities	sensory motor skills	Names of games that form motor skills and abilities
1.	Walking one behind the other in the ranks	Train	Self-fastening and unbuttoning	diligent child	Throwing the ball with both hands forward or up	Throw up
2.	Walking (zigzag) snake	snake	Collects small toys in a box	Tie your shoelace	Throwing a sandbag	drop it
3.	Walking in a column one or two without holding hands	Relay race	Stringing large beads onto a thread	Creative play	Reception of the thrown ball	catch the ball
four.	Stepping around objects	Nimble	Correctly holds a pencil-dash and a finger brush	Painting	Rolling the ball with two hands	Pass the ball!
five.	Running with a change in direction of movement	Victory is ours	Places the shapes in the appropriate places	Geometric board	Throwing the ball forward with both hands	Creative ball games

In the course of the pedagogical experiment, a statistically significant change was revealed (with a significance level of $p < 0.05$) in the control group in the height of the subjects ($t_{st} = 2.57$), in weight ($t_{st} = 2.63$) and in the results of throwing a 150 gram bag with sand ($t_{st} = 2.55$). For the remaining three indicators (the values of t_{st} changed between 1.72 and 1.85), statistically insignificant changes were observed during the pedagogical experiment ($p > 0.05$). Body height, weight, growth dynamics for the selected exercises: running 10 meters, long jumps from a place, throwing a 150 gram bag of sand, jumping with a jump rope of 6-7 year old test subjects of the experimental and control groups preparing for school during the pedagogical experiment are shown in percent (Figure 2).

In the control group preparing for school, the largest increase (10.51%) occurred in the weight of the subjects, as well as when the subjects ran 10 meters (8.17%), the smallest increase (4.85%) was found in jumping length from a place, the average growth rate in the control group was 7.49%.

There was a superiority of results during the pedagogical experiment in all exercises of preschool children of the experimental group over the results of the control group. In particular, for the four exercises studied in the control group, the arithmetic mean of the relative growth was 13.32%, the smallest relative increase was observed in the subject's heart rate (HR) per minute - 4.66%, the largest relative increase in the dynamometry of the right hand amounted to 9.33%.

Figure 2 Growth dynamics for the selected exercises of 6-7-year-old subjects preparing for school in the experimental and control groups during the pedagogical experiment (%).

In children of older preschool age, i.e. For the 6-7 year old control group, the arithmetic mean growth value for 3 exercises learned was 6.96%, the smallest relative increase in this group was found in the energy spent during the distance for 20 minutes - 5.89%, the largest increase was observed in the number steps taken by the subject within 20 minutes - 7.60%.

The indicators of the motor activity of the subjects of the experimental group changed during the pedagogical experiment, the smallest changes occurred in the energy spent by the subjects when passing the distance for 20 minutes - 8.89% and the largest changes in the number of steps taken by the subjects for 20 minutes - 15.50% , the average increase in results for three exercises in the experimental group was 13.17% (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Dynamics of changes in the results of physical activity of 6-7-year-old subjects preparing for school in the experimental and control groups (%).

From the results of the experiment, it became known that if in the 3-4 year old CG brought up according to the traditional program the body length and weight increased by 4.96 and 10.59%, respectively, by the end of the experiment, then in the EG brought up according to the optimized experimental program these indicators were 6.36% and 12.02%. Similarly, the physical abilities (10 m run, standing long jump and throwing 150 gram weight) in children from the EG were

characterized by faster growth than in children from the CG, i.e. the growth rate of speed-strength ability in this group rose to 9.72-16.58% ($P < 0.001$). And in the CG these indicators are equal to 5.68-6.56% ($P > 0.05$).

Arithmetic mean values of the results for test exercises selected for the study of speed-strength qualities, and indicators of physical development (anthropometry) in the age context of children in the experimental groups of preschool age of younger (3-4 years), middle (4-5 years), older (5-6 years old) and preparatory to school (6-7 years old) groups, a high and statistically significant increase in the EG indicators compared to the results of the CG during the pedagogical experiment (in 3-4 year old children, the CG 6.35%, the EG 13.35%; in 4-5 year old CG 6.74%, EG 14.92%; in 5-6 year old CG 7.22%, EG 14.30%; in 6-7 year old CG 6.96% and EG 13, 17%) indicate that the method of physical education developed by us and applied in the experimental group is more effective than the traditional program used in the control group.

Findings. Based on the results of a pedagogical experiment conducted to determine the motor activity of children, their analysis, conclusions and mutual comparison of recorded statistical indicators, it was found that the arithmetic mean values of the results shown by age in the experimental group of preschool children during the pedagogical experiment are relatively higher than the results control groups of the corresponding age (in 3-4 year old children in the CG 7.03% and in the EG 11.26%; in 4-5 year olds in the CG 7.87%, in the EG 12.67%; in 5-6 year olds in the CG 8.15%, in the EG - 13.34%; in 6-7 year olds in the CG - 7.49%, for the EG - 14.16%) and they changed statistically significantly progressively. This indicates a higher efficiency of the program developed by us and applied in the experimental group compared to the traditional program used in the control group.

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